

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MARONGIU****FIRST NAME: CRISTINA-IOANA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

1. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13–14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15–23)
3. American versus British English (McArthur 2002, 16)
4. Using templates and styles (Cleenewerck 2016, 10:23)
5. Latin abbreviations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 59–64)

A GUIDE TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Based on two given study materials (ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1 and Basic ACA-401 Tutorial), this response paper aims to both marshal essential information needed to apply to further academic writing on a doctoral level but also to challenge some of the in-situ presented concepts which are totally new to me and to my professional experience, as an educator for the secondary level in Germany, where I teach to a public Gymnasium close to Berlin. After having read the extensive coursepack and watched the related video, I decided to tackle the following subject matters without ignoring the entirety of the presented information: some rules of thumb for writing papers, punctuations, American versus British English, the use of templates and styles and, finally, Latin abbreviations. The choice of these key points may have to do with either a sheer interest in the presented aspects or a possible addition/challenge to them.

2) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

The ACA-401D coursepack presents some rules of thumb regarding essay writing, which I found the most interesting of the entire coursepack. More specifically, the subchapter “Some rules of thumb” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13–14) gives practical advice on how to address arguments in the introduction, conclusion, and body while

keeping the focus engaged, avoiding, for example, unclarity, like “polysyllabophilia” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13) or too general statements like: “For millennia human beings have searched for truth.” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13). I agree that such aspects need to be strongly taken into consideration in order to ensure consistency with the subject matter, as well as the right fluency in both writing and understanding (on the reader’s side) the particularities in question.

However, there are two aspects that caught my attention and which I find challenging. Page 13 from the above-cited coursepack indicates a positive example in line 2: “I will argue that...” This is a very challenging introduction for me as it clearly goes against the standard formats we, as educators, teach to our future alumni: when dealing with the advanced English course, the German Curriculum states that in the case of written papers, like comments or discussions, such personalized sentences are to be strictly avoided (MBJS, n.d., 2,5). In the same way, future university students are taught to be as objective as possible in their writings/papers therefore, passive constructions are actually encouraged in order to strengthen an objective perspective of arguments and counter-arguments (see to this regard page 13, lines 32-24 (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13). I suppose both the German Ministry of Education and Euclid University are right to a certain extent, and that is more up to the writer to choose the indicated tone and diction of his/her paper in order to be convincing enough and to rightly back up his/her arguments with examples or evidence, without being penalized for the chosen syntax. It is my hope that fluency and logic will play a bigger role in the academic style, regardless of its subjective or objective approach.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

As a passionate about grammar rules in foreign languages, I must admit that I enjoyed the chapter on punctuations from the coursepack very much (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15–23). Not only did it remind me of certain important grammar rules (regardless of whether they were British or American English), but it also successfully pointed out, through clear examples and analogies, the errors to avoid in various contexts. I found this chapter extremely useful and handy. However, seeing the plethora of examples and of situations very similar to one another, I would have preferred a logical explanation to each situation, like for example, on page 16, where the difference between “its” and “it’s” is not clearly made: one being a possession adjective (an attribute in a sentence), while the other case being about two distinct words, i.e., a subject and a predicate, with a different function in the same sentence, therefore they must be written separately. I believe that such clear, logical distinctions between words and their functions, whether as such or within a sentence, are a better way not to forget important differences between similar constructions.

Another example would be the n-dash usage examples (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 20), where there should be a clear distinction between the adjective up-to-date and the adverbial phrase “up to date.” Maybe in this manner, errors will be easier avoided, and errors will be easier avoided more easily. All in all, it was one of the most interesting chapters to read from the coursepack.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

In a world of constant access to all languages and accents, where the English language has become by far the global communication language, and where, due to practice and regular usage, differences are being reduced and simplified, I find such a subject difficult but also important to consider. My personal studies (in universities with intensive English courses) and professional career have made me acquainted with both British and American language variants, creating an impossible-to-avoid “melting pot” of “standardized” general English in everyday oral usage, whereas, in the written form, the rules of grammar and spelling are (hopefully) still applied. The Euclid coursepack rightly points out various differences from spelling and pronunciation up to false friends, grammar, and syntax usage (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 27). One very clear example is the different spelling of certain words with the vowel “o” (US English) versus “ou” (British English), like “color” versus “colour,” except for the word “glamour,” which unexplainably remains the same (in British and American English). However, it is mentioned that a hybridized and standardized form of English has gained momentum and that it has acquired a “position of global pre-eminence,” acting like a “lingua franca, metalanguage or a default mode” (McArthur 2002, 16). That is to say, we are facing a future where these variants will slowly diminish and be reduced to unwanted redundancies.

5) USING TEMPLATES AND STYLES

This key concept makes reference mainly to the video tutorial presented by Professor Cleenewerck regarding templates, styles, creating a response paper, choosing between the British and American styles, the differences between a rule of style and a paragraph style, citations, and sentence structures (Cleenewerck, 2016). In particular, I found useful and helpful his explanations regarding the differences between a rule of style and a paragraph style, where the professor shows how one can choose and navigate between headings, quotes styles, references, and normal styles (Cleenewerck, 2016, 10:23). I find such information very useful in structuring a clear and ordinated paper, where the contents indicate legibly where to find titles, subtitles, and paragraphs with their topic sentences and the related quotes, if applicable, and how to interchange these if needed. I concur with the need to apply such structure and organization, especially to academic papers of a certain length. The practical, right-on-spot clarification video was very helpful in creating the first response paper for EUCLID.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

As a polyglot with a multilingual and multicultural background, I have always been fascinated by foreign languages (the more, the better) and by their interconnectedness (linguistically or etymologically) in various contexts. One such language is Latin, which, luckily, can still be applied to different texts in various languages without changing the meaning; on the contrary, adding a plus of excellence, as well as common ground

and common sense at the same time. The ACA-401D coursepack gathers a concise list of Latin words and phrases (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 59–64), which are sure to be of aid during the writing process of an academic paper. As an Italian native speaker, I was familiar with over 50% of the idioms presented, but I was still unfamiliar with words and structures such as *eadem*, *scilicet*, and *passim*. *In toto invenio hoc opus utile*.

7) CONCLUSION

Going through the ACA-401D coursepack, its Basic Tutorial video and, after a duly consideration of each of the key points presented above, I can conclude that this has helped me greatly in setting the tone not only for my first response paper but also the upcoming papers towards the final goal of my doctoral thesis. As stated above, there are challenges and things to consider, as not everything will be immediately 100% understood and applied. Yet, I have great faith and hope that this is the beginning of a fruitful collaboration and individual growth on an academic and personal level. Thank you to my supervisors and instructors for being on my side throughout this incredible endeavor.

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